

A digital species index: an underrated tool for natural history collections

Mr Luc Willemse¹

¹*Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Nederland*

Digitisation of natural history collections has been ongoing for quite some time now. It opened up data held in natural history collections in an unprecedented way. Collection digitisation is usually linked to if not considered synonymous with specimen digitisation. Although specimen digitisation is the single most important level of digitisation in natural history collections, it is very time consuming. Depending on available resources and the goals we want to achieve, there is also another level of digitisation to be considered. This presentation will zoom in on the digital species index: the result of digitising natural history collections at the species level. Based on recent efforts undertaken at the Academy of Natural Sciences of Drexel University (Philadelphia) and Naturalis (Leiden) to create a digital species index, the presentation will look into workflows, planning and costs. The added value of digital species indexes will be illustrated with examples. Challenges and issues linked to species indexes will be highlighted and some recommendations and lessons learned shared.

